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Ideological Strategy through *Halal* Certification Media Implemented by Policy Makers, Producers, and Consumers

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Abstract

This research departed from producer's behavior in promoting their product through Islamic sharia approach using halal certification or religious media to make the people interested in consuming them. Such condition encouraged the author to study more deeply the halal certificate as an ideology. In this research, data collection was carried out through observation, interview, and document. Field observation on the application of halal to product and media applied in restaurants. Direct interview was carried out with the policy makers of Indonesian Ulema Councils; producers representing corporations and Micro-, small-, and medium-scale enterprises; consumers, and media and branding experts related to halal label. Data constitutes data relating to halal label media and its promotion media. The data was validated using triangulation process and analyzed using ideological approach. The finding of research shows that there are four types of ideology relating to halal certification: capitalism obliging products to have halal certificate; socialism applying halal certification as prestige; authoritarianism generating pros and cons on halal label; and democracy performed by the people to deal with the implementation of halal product.

Keywords: *ideology, halal, organizing institution, producer, consumer, product*

INTRODUCTION

Producers and sellers want the products they sell bought by consumers by means of providing *halal* attribute. The consumers' decision in choosing product is based on need, attractive packaging, and *halal* label (Irfan et al., 2024). *Halal* label, according to Jagdish Sheth, perceives the presence of the following components: religious value, security, health, and exclusivity (Mardiyati & Wahyudi, 2020)

Halal is not only *sunnah* that should be applied to the product bought but has also been lifestyle so that the producers lead their product marketing to the community caring about health and healthy lifestyle, and following *halal* principle (Juliana et al., 2024) In the presence of such components, the consumers will trust the product better and will consume it stilly, because it is considered having small risk, moreover the product includes *halal* label. The presence of *halal* label can help the consumers find out the condition of product to be consumed as *halal* product (Ilyas, 2017). *Halal* is each of producers' expectation that the product they sell will be trusted by the consumers consuming it.

To Muslim consumers, buying *halal* product is a belief as the main consideration (Wan et al., 2014). *Halal* is the command of Islamic sharia law to be undertaken by Muslim community. It is based on this *sharia* law that Indonesian Ulema Council (Indonesian: Majelis Ulama Indonesia) endeavors to issue a *fatwa* (official opinion relating to Islamic law) regarding the obligation of having *halal* certificate for the food and beverage product circulating in the market. *Halal* product is the main factor, because consuming *halal* food is the religion's command that should be undertaken by a Muslim, including the producer the target market of which is Muslims (Azis et al., 2023). In addition, Muslim community also really considers a product to be consumed and they will be still in the presence of *halal* guarantee (Sulaksono & Azizah, 2022).

The first *halal* certification was a result of *fatwa ijtihad* issued by Indonesian Ulema Council as the legal status of a product traded, as written in in the Decree of Indonesian Ulema Council No. Kep-

018/MUI/1989. In the presence of the decree, all food, beverage, and cosmetic products should register to the Indonesian Ulema Council's Food, Drug, and Cosmetics Research Institution (Indonesian: *Lembaga Pengkajian Pangan, Obat-Obatan dan Kosmetik Majelis Ulama Indonesia* or LPPOM-MUI) to get *halal* certificate for two years and it can be extended for the two following years, and so forth (Erliani & Sobiroh, 2022). Based on social, cultural, and psychological aspects, *halal* predicate can motivate Muslim community to consume a product so that it can be the target consumers (Khemakhem & Karoui, 2019).

Consumers with religiosity-related behavior buy product not only based on function, taste, and price but also based on religion related to *halal* certification (Jusmaliani & Nasution, 2021). Through religiosity ideology, the producers know how important a certification of product is, and thereby they really consider the importance of image of product brand with *halal* certification. The producers know that in buying food and beverage products, majority consumers look for the ones with *halal* certification and label (Djunaidi et al., 2021). A study entitled *Exploring Consumer Attitudes toward Halal Products* concluded that the purchase of *halal*-certified products is important to consumers (Demirel & Yasarsoy, 2017).

The Chairperson of *Halal* Product Guarantee Organizing Agency (Indonesian: *Kepala Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Produ Halal*)'s Decree Number 88 of 2022 about the use of *halal* label in the Product Having Obtained *Halal* Certificate states that *halal* label can be put on display of promotion media, packaging design, merchandise, stationary corporate, pennant, billboard, and promotion event (The Chairperson of Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of Halal Product's Decree Number 88 of 2022, 2022). Based on the decree, the producers can advertise its *halal* product to the public in various promotion media, with Muslim consumers being its target market (Shah et al. 2019). Similarly, it can be promoted on the packaging as the link between producers and consumers in marketing their product based on religious belief and personal benefit of both Muslim and non-Muslim consumers (Sungnoi & Soonthonmai, 2024).

The *halal* label is so sacred viewed from the perspectives of organizer, the institution issuing *halal* certification to the producers having product and the consumers as the buyer of product that hegemony system is established between from the ruler over the controlled one. *Halal* label and promotion media are a means of hegemony ideology to legitimize power through visual and verbal appeals as the representation of idea through hegemony strategy taken by the institution issuing *halal* label to producers and then to consumers (Rosniar et al., 2013). It is this hegemony ideology that makes the author interested in researching and studying more in-depth rightfulness (*kehalalan*) within society. Therefore, to find out and to understand the *halal* label, the author combines and adapts *halal* products to Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) or Agency for Organizing Guarantee of *Halal* Product (BPJPH), producers, and consumers relating to ideological approach.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research aims to analyze the role of *halal* certification and its effect on the organizing institution, producer, and consumer delivered in information and promotion media visually and verbally. The approach used was qualitative ideological media employed by the organizing institution and producers regarding its product delivered visually and verbally to the public as the product buyers.

The first step of data collection was observation conducted directly on producers and consumers' behavior toward the rightfulness (*kehalalan*) of product applied in the society. To support the data of observation, documentation data was collected in the form of photographs of promotion media including packaging design, banner, name of restaurant, and *halal*-supporting property related to the product sold. These data were obtained when the author conducted field research observation relating to *halal* applied by the consumers in the society.

Then, direct interview was carried out with a business actor, Aris Sugiyanto (41 years) constituting an owner Jordan Bakery Home Industry in Malang Regency; a policy maker, Muhammad Qusyairi (64 years) as the Vice Chairperson of Indonesian Ulema Council of Malang City; inter-religion consumers including Kadek Jaya Sumanggala (28 years) as the Buddhist monk from Kertarajasa Convent of Batu City and Ellyastuti (23 year) often attending service in St. Antonius Catholic Church of Purbayan, Surakarta; and observers of promotion and branding media including Bejo Rianto (66 years) as an advertising media expert from Surakarta and Agung Eko Budi Waspada (58 years) as the expert of branding media from Bandung.

For the data to be more valid, triangulation was carried out through data sources and types of data objects collected from different perspectives. The analysis was carried out using Gramsci's theory of ideology, the existence of societal power in organizing by the more dominant over the less dominant (Jaques et al., 2019). In the hegemony of *halal* certification, there is power and authority in the Indonesian Ulema Council or the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of *Halal* Product Guarantee over producers and consumers to use some methods to influence consumers through media and discourses considered true (Juditha, 2018). All the results of data collection and analysis were grouped into four main sub-topics: the presence of *halal* as an ideology, *halal* ideology as prestige, pros and cons of *halal* ideology, and investigation of *halal* ideology. These sub-topics explore the practice of *halal* certification ideology applied by policy makers and producers to consumers through: Capitalistic Ideology, Socialist Ideology, Authoritarian Ideology, and Democratic Ideology.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Indonesia is very rich in food and beverage that can be consumed to spoil the tongue and stomach. Indonesia is famous for its various spices that can create various variations of food and beverage having rich flavors. The combination of creativity, tradition, aesthetics, and local wisdom as elements can enhance the taste and value of the product (Auliya & Mona, 2020). Based on the observations of many types of consumer products that are almost on the market as competitor products, numerous variants of similar products give the public a note regarding the quality of the products consumed so that producers use various methods through services to obtain *halal* predicate, as stated by Aris Sugiyanto (interview, January 14, 2025), that his Jordan Bakery product initially did not have a *halal* label and was less popular among consumers, after the *halal* label was attached to the bread packaging, his turnover increased by 120%.

Halal-labeled products are intended not only to countries with Muslim populations, but also to countries with Muslim minorities, because they are based on ongoing knowledge of *halal* services for all life (Susilawati et al., 2021). *Halal* products, in fact, are the main choice for non-Muslims to consume, as stated by one of the mass participants at the St. Antonius Catholic Church in Surakarta, Ellyastuti (interview, February 12, 2025), according to her, *halal*-labeled products provide tranquility in consuming because they have product quality standards. This opinion is similar to the statement of Kadek Jaya Sumanggala (interview, January 21, 2025) as a Buddhist monk saying that the existence of a *halal* label makes his heart comfortable in consuming because the quality of product has been tested. *Halal* products are increasingly popular among the consumers, including non-Muslims, who are considered to have the following aspects: religious values, health, safety, exclusivity, intentions and purchasing attitudes (Zaimah et al., 2018).

A policy maker in Indonesian Ulema Council of Malang City, Muhammad Qusyairi (interview, January 9 2025), said that the writing of *halal* label is close to Arabic culture as a parameter for Muslims. In 1989, the first *halal* label was attached to food and beverage products. *Halal* is the result of a fatwa of *ij'tihad* as an Islamic legal status in determining *halal* certification for products. The opposite of *halal* is *haram* (illicit or prohibited). *Halal* is the obligation of Muslims to consume food and beverage and use goods according to Islamic law. *Haram* are activities and actions that are prohibited in the Islamic religion so that Muslims stay away from or avoid the products they will consume and use.

Looking at the development of *halal* certification starting from the administrators, i.e. the Food, Drug and Cosmetics Assessment Institution under the Indonesian Ulema Council and the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of *Halal* Product of the Indonesian Ministry of Religion; users, including Companies and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises; and connoisseurs, i.e. the purchaser community, there are several ideologies used: (1) the ideology of capitalism discussed in the sub-topic: the presence of *halal* as an ideology; (2) the ideology of socialism in the sub-topic: the ideology of *halal* as prestige; (3) the ideology of authoritarianism in the sub-topic: the pros and cons of *halal* ideology; and (4) the ideology of democracy discussed in the sub-topic: investigation of *halal* ideology.

The Presence of *Halal* as an Ideology

Vice Chairman of Indonesian Ulema Council of Malang City, Muhammad Qusyairi (interview, January 9, 2025), explained that the emergence of *halal* label was due to public concerns about the circulation of lard in 1988, so that the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) issued Decree Number

Kep./18/MUI/I/1989 on January 6, 1989 in establishing the Indonesian Ulema Council's Food and Drug Supervision Research Institute (LPPOM-MUI) the task of which is to examine *halal* certification on products circulating in the community (Azis et al., 2023). It was in 1989 that the *halal* label appeared written in Arabic letters *Khat Riq'ah* "حلال" (*halal*) combined with a circular line surrounding it. This is a capitalistic ideological strategy, as a socio-economic system of personal ownership on the part of the ruler to gain profit alone (*The Ideology of Capitalism*, 2023), just like the capitalistic ideology carried out by the Indonesian Ulema Council against corporations and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises requiring *halal* certification for the food and beverages they produce. The Indonesian Ulema Council argues that this is intended to enable the user community to consume the product stilly.

An advertising media expert from Surakarta, Bejo Rianto (interview, February 25, 2025) said that the label derived from the Latin word *signare* meaning to mark. Generally, a label is an identity or sign with special characteristics applied to objects considered appropriate, such as the *halal* label applied to food and beverage products. *Halal* certification is a prestigious religious predicate for a product that is always hoped for and dreamed of by every corporation. The certification launched in 1989 is a *halal* predicate issued by the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI). In the eyes of corporations and home industry entrepreneurs, according to Aris Sugiyanto (interview, January 14, 2025), when the *halal* label was first introduced, it was not familiar to companies and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises because it was considered to have no impact on their products. Likewise, in its application, the 1989 *halal* label was displayed on product packaging, making consumers feel doubtful and skeptical about the products they were going to buy (Damit et al., 2017)

In its development, the *halal* label is very much needed and is a source of pride for corporations and home industry entrepreneurs because it can be used as an information media and promotional media for their products to the public. Muhammad Qusyairi (interview, January 9, 2025) said that the *halal* label was replaced with the new different one in 2007, inscribed with Arabic letters *Khat Koufi* written in a circle, as stated in the Indonesian Ulema Council's Decree number: SK10 / Dir / LP POM MUI / XII / 07. Through this decree, the old *halal* label was no longer valid and was replaced with a new *halal* label launched in 2007. The *halal* label is, according to Aris Sugiyanto (interview, January 14, 2025), indeed very tempting so that corporations and home industry entrepreneurs want to display it in information and promotional media even in the wrong way, by imitating it without having to get permission from the Indonesian Ulema Council. Capitalist ideology is also carried out by corporations and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises to the public so that they want their products sold in the market. The most disadvantaged in this condition is, of course, the community as the final destination for product buyers who are seduced by the *halal* label.

In further development in 2009, the Indonesian Ulema Council issued a new policy requiring domestic and foreign food and beverage products entering Indonesia to have *halal* labels with Arabic *Khat Koufi* letters and a *halal* certificate number from LPPOM-MUI written on its bottom. Muhammad Qusyairi (interview, January 9, 2025) said that the public follows the development of *halal* certification for the food and beverage products they buy. The public pays attention to the product packaging that includes *halal* label using Arabic *Khat Riq'ah* letters written in a circle and *halal* certificate number on its bottom. Muhammad Qusyairi (interview, January 9, 2025) added that a *halal* certificate has a 14-digit number, for example the certificate number: 01-15-116934-0620, meaning as follows: digits 1-2 representing the LPPOM area code; digits 3-4 representing the type of product being certified; digits 5-10 representing the certificate sequence number; and digits 11-14 representing the month and year when the certification was issued. The existence of the 14-digit number is a capitalistic ideological strategy taken by the Indonesian Ulema Council to narrow the marketing movement for corporations and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises that are considered stubborn and do not want to register their products to obtain *halal* certification.

The *halal* label has changed since March 1, 2022, again due to the transfer of *halal* certification authority from the Food, Drug, and Cosmetics Research Institution of the Indonesian Ulema Council (LPPOM MUI) to the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of *Halal* Product (BPJPH) of the Republic of Indonesia's Ministry of Religion (Detikcom, 2022) The Secretary of BPJPH, Arfi Hatim, said that based on number 40 of 2022 *Halal* Labels is determined in the form of a dome or mountain shape and a *Surjan* motif or lyrics symbolizing humans living in the harmony of faith (HUMAS, 2022). Arabic letters in *kufi* script consist of "Ha", "Lam Alif", and "Lam" to create the word "*Halal*". The *halal* label is purple meaning faith,

unity of body and soul and having the power of imagination (The Chairperson of Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of Halal Product's Decree Number 88 of 2022, 2022). Agung Eko Budi Waspada (interview, February 17, 2025) said that the *halal* label implemented in 2022 is a very simple and communicative work because it is visible, readable, and memorable to the public consuming and using the products they buy. This *halal* label applies a capitalistic ideology to certification organizers, including the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of *Halal* Product, for those apply for certification including business actors and the public as product buyers.

The Food, Drug, and Cosmetics Research Institution of Indonesian Ulema Council manages *halal* certification based on its label having undergone three decades of changes, in 1989, 2007, and 2009 in the form of a green circle. It, according to branding expert Agung Eko Budi Waspada (interview, February 17, 2025), is the application of Islamic sharia ideology regarding *halal* products. Food, beverage, drug, and cosmetic products sold must be *halal*-certified because they are related directly to the humans using them. In 2022 there was a transfer of authority over *halal* certification from the Food, Drug, and Cosmetics Research Institution of the Indonesian Ulema Council to the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of *Halal* Product, according to (Permana, 2022) as stated in Number 40 of 2022 concerning the Determination of *Halal* Labels. Thus, there was a major change in the *halal* label in 2022 into a purple mountain shape having an imaginative ideology to develop for its organizer, the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of *Halal* Product of the Ministry of Religion, as shown in Figure 1. Therefore, the management of the *halal* certification budget does not belong to the responsibility of the religious institution of the Indonesian Ulema Council, but it is covered by the funds coming from the community for the certification of product entering the country through the Indonesia's Ministry of Religion.

Figure 1:
Halal Labels released in 1989, 2007, 2009, and 2022
Source: Indonesian Ulema Council and Ministry of Religion

Halal certification is carried out continuously and always monitored for food, drug and cosmetic products sold in the market. Products displaying the label *halal* in 1989, 2007, and 2009 on information and promotional media are no longer valid, because what is valid currently is the label issued in 2022. This is a capitalistic ideology viewed from the transfer of the management of *halal* certification from previously the Food, Drug, and Cosmetics Research Institution under the Indonesian Ulema Council with a green *halal* Arabic letter label with *kufi khat* to the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of *Halal* Product of the Indonesian Ministry of Religion with a purple mountain-shaped *halal* label. The government power is enacted as a capitalistic ideology in managing *halal* certification through the Indonesian Ministry of Religion, meaning that the Indonesian Ulema Council is no longer allowed to manage it, according to Law No. 33 of 2014 concerning *Halal* Product Guarantee.

***Halal* Ideology as Prestige**

Based on his first experience in managing *halal* certification, Aris Sugiyanto (interview, January 14, 2025), the process was so long in 1989 and full of twists and turns that had to be passed through until finally a *halal* certificate was obtained from the Food, Drug and Cosmetics Research Institution of the Indonesian Ulema Council. To obtain a *halal* certificate, full struggle, high dedication, concentration and seriousness are required, and the rules specified by the certification organizer must be obeyed. It took a long time to finally obtain a *halal* certificate for several of his products. He displayed the *halal* label on information and

promotional media as seen by researchers on the packaging of his Jordan Bakery. Through the ideology of socialism, the *halal* label can create close relationship between producers and consumers, because the products produced are accepted by the community stilly without any pressure.

Having a *halal* certificate for the goods it produces is a *prestige* to a corporation. *Halal* is a level of quality specified in Islamic law approved and issued by the Food, Drug, and Cosmetics Research Institution of the Indonesian Ulema Council or the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of Halal Product of Indonesian Ministry of Religion for products produced by producers or Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. Aris Sugiyanto (interview, January 14, 2025) said that he is proud that his product can pass through *halal* certification successfully. The existence of this certification means that the *halal* label is always displayed on the product packaging so that consumers are more confidence in the products they buy. This confirms that consumers will be more confident and stiller if there is a *halal* label on the packaging, because the majority (80%) of the community is Muslim. In purchasing products, Muslims Indonesians, according to Muhammad Qusyairi (interview January 9, 2025), firstly pay attention to the *halal* label attached to the products they buy. *Halal*-certified products are the responsibility of producers to produce quality products, protected products, and products recognized by the government and liked by the community. This condition, as a form of socialist ideology, is a political economic system owned and managed by community groups through government monitoring (Adam et al., 2024)

The *halal* certification program carried out by the Indonesian Ulema Council and the Ministry of Religion is one way taken by the Indonesian government to standardize products that have *halal* status. Likewise, corporations and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises have added value where their employees prepared *halal* products. Through this *halal* certificate, corporations and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises are no longer awkward in promoting their products. *Halal* certificates, according to Bejo Rianto (25, February 2025), benefit corporations and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises when it is displayed on product packaging, because they can attract the attention of consumers, especially Muslims. The attachment of *halal* labels to promotional media must not be arbitrary, because it is regulated in the Director of LPPOM MUI's Decree Number: SK10 / Dir / LPPOM MUI / XI / 07 concerning the attachment and use of *halal* labels (IHATEC, 2021)

The main segmentation of *halal* products is the Muslim community, because the number of Muslims in Indonesia will reach 244,712,757 people in 2025 out of a total population of 281,279,031 people (Muhaimin, 2025). The expenditure of Indonesian Muslims for *halal* product services in 2025 will increase by around 14.96% or about USD281.6 billion (Perindustrian, 2024). Indonesia is the country with the largest Muslim population in the world, producing *halal* products to balance the gap in the domestic *halal* market comparable to foreign production (Sazali & Saidi, 2024). Indonesia, as a country with the large Muslim population, utilizes the potential for the world *halal* product consumption in 2027 which is projected to be around USD3.1 trillion with an annual growth rate of around 4.8% (Perindustrian, 2024). The ideology of socialism is carried out by producers in targeting the flexibility market, in which not only the Muslim community chooses products that have been *halal*-certified, but non-Muslim community will also stiller when they consume *halal* products. It is in line with Kadek Jaya Sumanggala (interview, January 21, 2025), a Buddhist, stating that in buying products he still prioritizes those with *halal* labels because they have been tested through clinical health and product quality.

Pros and Cons of Halal Ideology

Halal certification is still desired by the community so that what is done gets the approval and reward of Allah SWT. If food and beverage sold and bought are *haram* (prohibited), of course they will not be blessed and gets reactions from the community, such as an incident occurring in the food seasoning product brand and Ajinomoto Company in Mojokerto, East Java, Indonesia. During the reign of President Abdul Rahman Wahid (Gus Dur) in 2001, the Indonesian Ulema Council ordered Ajinomoto to withdraw its products from the market because it was suspected of being *haram* for consumption (Nasyi'ah, 2018). The Indonesian Ulema Council stated that Ajinomoto products were declared *haram* because they used *bacto soytone* containing a pork enzyme called porcine.

The Ajinomoto Company was protested by the public at that time because its products were considered to contain porcine enzymes/lards functioning to accelerate the process of monosodium glutamate

production. The public reaction was even worse when they demonstrated on Jalan Raya Mlirip No. 110, precisely in front of the PT. Ajinomoto Company. The Japanese company received special attention from Gus Dur. If it was left alone it would spread widely and result in cracks in the relationship between the two countries: Indonesia and Japan. So Gus Dur intervened to resolve the bad image of the Japanese company. At that time Gus Dur issued a Warrant for the Cease of Investigation (SP3) regarding the Ajinomoto case (Merdeka.com). This letter was, according to Agung Eko Budi Waspada (interview, February 17, 2025), the ideology of Gus Dur's policy in clarifying that Ajinomoto's products did not contain porcine enzymes/lards, and thereby the product was declared *halal* (Liputan6. 2001). Finally, the Indonesian Ulema Council issued a fatwa on flavor enhancer products (monosodium glutamate, MSG) stating that the product of PT. Ajinomoto Indonesia using *mameno* is *halal* (MUI, 2001).

The problem faced by Ajinomoto is that there are opposing views between the religious institution of the Indonesian Ulema Council and the Indonesian Government regarding *halal* and *haram*. This incident, as a practice of authoritarian ideology, occurs when one objected to the same rules because each has different principles based on the mechanisms used and implemented (Dinas & Northmore-Ball, 2016). This ideology was implemented by the advertising star of an Ajinomoto product, Mandra, who terminated his employment relationship, resigned from his job as a model in promoting the product and did not want to continue his work contract with the Ajinomoto Company. This condition requires a clear mind to restore the reputation of the product and the Ajinomoto Company among the people. Various methods were used, one of which was to advertise the product in various advertising media starring Deddy Mizwar paired with Paramitha Rusadhy (an actor and an actrist) wearing Muslim clothing (Chandra, 2010). Based on observation of the advertisement, the two models only conveyed the deliciousness of Ajinomoto products, but the public already understood the symbol of the clothing worn by the advertising models as a sign of the rightfulness (*kehalalan*) of the product being promoted. This advertisement is according to Bejo Rianto (interview, February 25, 2025), a propaganda tool for the Islamic sharia ideology strategy regarding the *kehalalan* of Ajinomoto products which are worthy of being accepted and consumed by the general public.

In 2016, there were pros and cons against the Zoya brand fashion products produced by PT Shafco Multi Trading to prospective buyers. This debate arose when the Zoya brand hijab received *halal* certification from the West Java representative office of Indonesian Ulema Council, with halal certificate number: 01171156041015. The reason for PT Shafco Multi Trading as a hijab manufacturer was that consumers would feel still because their products had *halal* certificates (Sari, 2016). *Halal* certification for hijabs has generated pros and cons in society. Some agree because it must be *halal* when worn by consumers, while others are restless because they feel constrained by *halal* products so that they cannot use them freely. *Halal* hijab products in Islamic law are not only in the model of covering the genitals, but can be seen from the material of the fabric, whether it is *halal* or *haram*. If we return to the law of *halal* and *haram*, indeed dressing, according to Islamic law, not only covers the genitals but is also free from impurities and *haram* things. Muhammad Qusyairi (interview, January 9, 2025) emphasized that all products coming into contact with the user's body parts require *halal* certification. This condition shows the appearance of an authoritarian ideology in promoting the products it sells through loopholes in Islamic sharia law seeming to force people to implement the truth of sharia law.

In 2017, there was an incident in Malaysia about suspicious *halal*-labeled brush and shoe products. Following the testing carried out in the Patra Malaysia University laboratory, it was discovered that the shoe material was made of pigskin and the brush was made of pig bristles. This product was confiscated by the Ministry of Domestic Trade's officers, because in Malaysia it is prohibited to sell products made of pork, unless the product is labeled *haram* and packaged and sold separately in shopping centers in Malaysia. This problem is, according to Muhammad Qusyairi (interview, January 9, 2025), a serious problem about religion based on Islamic law regarding *halal* and *haram*. Viewed from the government's side, there is a need for an authoritarian ideology in determining legal cases, that anyone who violates the *halal* status will be threatened with a fine of 100,000 ringgit or around IDR 300 million, or substituted with a maximum imprisonment of 3 years (Chan, 2017).

In 2024, there was a violation of the *Halal* Product Guarantee regulation committed by PT ARF producing Okko bread. Based on product testing conducted on Okko bread by the *Halal* Product Guarantee Agency of the Ministry of Religion, the product was found containing hazardous materials in the form of

Sodium Dehydroacetate as a preservative, referring to the Government Regulation Number 39 of 2021 article 149 about the violation incident of administrative sanctions. Although Okko bread has received *halal* certification on June 27, 2023 with the certificate number: ID00210006483580623, the *halal* certificate no longer prevailed (BPJPH, 2024) since August 1, 2024 due to the violation. This is due to the authoritarian ideology on the part of the *Halal* Product Guarantee Agency as its responsibility as the organizer of *halal* certification so that the products consumed by the public should be truly healthy. If a product has received a *halal* certificate, it needs to be implemented consistently and its rightfulness (*kehalalan*) must be maintained.

Dealing with *Halal* Ideology

In the hearts of consumers, the *halal* label is highly expected to always be attached to products circulating in the community, through product packaging media and other promotional media. The greatness of the *halal* label that can captivate prospective buyers lead corporations and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises unable to manage or finance it to find shortcuts, through displaying fake *halal* labels to deceive prospective consumers to make their products purchased. It has been found in the market that some food products are wrapped with packaging displaying old labels from 1989, 2007, and 2009 even though they have been changed since 2022. This method is, according to Muhammad Qusyairi (interview, January 9, 2025), clearly detrimental to consumers, because the products sold do not have a *halal* certificate from the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of Halal Product of Indonesian Ministry of Religion. In the code of ethics, Agung Eko Budi Waspada (interview, February 17, 2025) emphasized that there is a prohibition on deceiving that is not in accordance with reality, because the products sold do not have a *halal* certificate.

Halal certification of products marketed to the public is a special concern for producers and sellers. They know that the majority of Indonesian people are Muslims required to consume *halal* products. Producers and sellers create strategies to enable their products to be purchased even though they do not have *halal* certification, by enticing buyers through packaging designs with the word *halal*. The author once found a home industry bread product with the packaging written “100% *halal*”, despite no *halal* label. At that time the author asked the producer, have you ever made 90%, 70%, or 50% bread products? The answer was never, all that was produced was 100%. It turned out that this bread producer had not been able to obtain *halal* certification for its products so that they use this method provisionally. This method According to Aris Sugiyanto (interview, January 14, 2025), is only a strategy for the interests of producers so that their products can be accepted and purchased by the public, it is better not to deceive the public because if they find out they will leave the products they have consumed.

For consumers not to violate the practice of selling their products, the ideology of democracy is implemented as a practice of giving freedom to the community so that people have the power to express themselves to educate themselves and others (Schwarm, 2017). If you do not have *halal* certificate, you can use other methods, just like the one used by the “Basmalah” cafe and the “Alhamdulillah” depot on Jalan Tlogomas Malang, East Java. Based on the author's observations, the two restaurants use Arabic “Basmalah” and “Alhamdulillah” and are supported by the property of waiters using *peci* (traditional head covering worn by Muslim males) and *jilbab* (a full-length outer garment, traditionally covering the head and hands, worn in public by some Muslim women) attached to the entire Muslim community, so that buyers can consume stilly. Aris Sugiyanto (interview, January 14, 2025) gave another example to show the rightfulness (*kehalalan*) of the products sold, the waiters can wear Muslim clothing as a symbol of Muslims characterizing *halal* food and beverage sold.

An observation was also conducted on the Ramen Japanese Restaurant located in Pakuwon Mall Solo Baru Surakarta. Researchers were interested in this restaurant because it was crowded with buyers queuing, both Muslims and non-Muslims. This crowd is, according to Kadek Jaya Sumanggala (interview, January 21, 2025) as a Buddhist, a marketing strategy with an Islamic law approach because it has met *halal* certification standards supported by its waiters wearing sar'i clothing, namely modest Muslim clothing that does not show body curves and covers the genitals. Although the product comes from Japan, it still follows the rules of the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of Halal Product of Indonesian Ministry of Religion. To strengthen the *halal* products sold, the restaurant put up a banner on the ceiling visually displaying pictures of two boys and girls wearing *peci* and *jilbab*. Likewise, the waiters wear *songkok* head coverings

and *jilbab* to confirm the message that what is being sold is a *halal* product. This, according to Agung Eko Budi Waspada (interview, February 17, 2025), is a strategy to compare products from Japan that have *halal* certification tempting consumers to buy them.

Some strategies to deal with rightfulness (*kehalalan*) are taken continuously by corporations and micro, small, and medium enterprises as a way to lure consumers to be interested in and to buy the products they sell. The strategy taken by business actors can be right and wrong. The promotion strategy taken rightly is to dramatize the product through an Islamic approach, such as the name of the restaurant using Arabic and using Islamic law properties. The promotion strategy taken wrongly is the one violating the rules of the Indonesian Ulema Council and the Indonesian Ministry of Religion, such as deceiving that its products have been *halal*-labeled even though they have never registered their products to obtain *halal* certification. The methods used by business actors are not only self-interested but also pay attention to and prioritize the interests of the community as buyers of the product.

CONCLUSION

The “*halal*” certificate is the ideology of the Indonesian Ulema Council and the Indonesian Ministry of Religion provided to producers to make their products meet Islamic sharia standards so that buyers feel comfortable in consuming them. The ideology is implemented by producers to make their products purchased by the public, through verbal and visual dramatization leading to *halal* which is informed in the media so that people know, are interested in, have desires, have beliefs, and take action to purchase products. This ideology is always applied by policy makers, in this case the Indonesian Ulema Council and the Indonesian Ministry of Religion, by business actors including Companies and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises so that their products are sell quickly in the market, and by consumers as buyers because of the obligation to carry out sharia and a sense of calm.

Halal certification is an ideological media that must be adhered to by various parties such as policy makers, including the Indonesian Ulema Council and the Indonesian Ministry of Religion; business actors, including Corporations and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises; and consumers as the end goal or product users. Viewed from its capacity, there are several ideologies: (1) Capitalistic ideology, because policy makers require products sold to have *halal* certification, the presence of *halal* certificates serves as an ideology; (2) Socialist ideology is on the side of Muslim and non-Muslim communities as consumers who choose *halal*, healthy, and safe products to consume; (3) Authoritarian ideology leads to regulations and policies implemented by the Agency for Organizing the Guarantee of Product of the Ministry of Religion to legalize products with *halal* certificates so that people can consume them stilly; and (4) Democratic ideology leads to producers having their own strategies through the Islamic sharia property approach even though their products do not yet have *halal* certification.

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